

EFFECT OF LEPROSY ON NON-ENZYMATIC ANTIOXIDANTS (VITAMIN C, VITAMIN E AND URIC ACID) IN (EDO STATE) NIGERIAN LEPROSY PATIENTS.

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ABSTRACT

In the study being reported, the plasma levels of vitamin C, vitamin E and uric acid were determined in a total of 86 subjects comprised of 31 leprosy patients on multidrug therapy (MBT), 40 leprosy patients relieved from therapy (RFT) in Ossiomo leprosarium settlement and 15 normal individuals who served as control subjects. Of the MDT group, 10 subjects were paucibacillary (PB) lepers and 21 multibacillary (MB) lepers. The results obtained show that there were significant decreases in the plasma vitamin C and vitamin E ($P < 0.05$) relative to the controls. However the uric acid was higher in the lepers ($P < 0.05$) compared with the control subject. The uric of the RFT patients (10.74 ± 0.99) obtained was significantly higher than those of MDT patients (2.90 ± 0.29) and controls (6.69 ± 0.32). There was significant increase ($P < 0.05$) in the uric acid of female RFT patients compared with the males. The decrease in the vitamin C and vitamin E levels in the leprosy patients could be as a result of the free radicals producing ability of the ant leprosy chemotherapy and the effect of *Mycobacterium leprae* during and after the chronic cause of the disease in the population studied.

KEY WORDS: leprosy, antioxidants, MDT, RFT, vitamin C, vitamin E, Uric acid Edo state, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Leprosy, also known as Hansen's disease is caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*. It is characterized by damage to the skin, peripheral nerves and the lining of the upper respiratory tract. As a result of the nerve damage, there may be paralysis, deformity and ulceration (Macleod, 1984). In 1984, World Health Organization (WHO 1998) listed Nigeria along with other countries such as Bangladesh, Brazil, India, Indonesia and Myanmar where the disease is still endemic (Jacobson and Krahenbuhl 1999).

Antioxidants according to Krinsky (1992) are compounds that protect biological systems against the potentially harmful effects of processes or reactions that can cause excessive oxidation (such as produced by this disease and drugs for its treatment). The destructive potentials of *M. leprae* (Macleod, 1984) and metabolic effects of the ant leprosy drugs are capable of producing oxidative damage to macromolecules, such as lipids, protein, carbohydrates and nucleic acid, ultimately leading to cells necrosis in patients (Halliwell and Gutleridge, 1989). Humans are well endowed with antioxidant defense mechanism against reactive oxygen species; among the oxidants are vitamins A, C and E, enzymes such as super oxide dismutase and catalase. However, just recently, uric acid has been added to the list (Waring, 2002). According to Beyer (1994) one of the roles of Vitamins C, A and E which can easily be administered is that of scavenging for free radicals in the aqueous phase of cells and the circulatory system to mop up generated reactive oxygen species ROS (Angel *et al*, 2002 Waring, 2002 and Squadrito *et al*, 2000).

One of the multidrug therapy (MDT) drugs for leprosy dapsone is strongly oxidative in a way that damages the membranes red blood cells and results in haemolysis. It was shown that combined therapy of Vitamin C and Vitamin E confers partial protective effects against dapsone-induced haemolysis in patients with dermatitis and herpetiformis (Lardo *et al*. 1997). In a similar manner, Vitamins A and E were used to relief mouth sores arising as common sides effects of chemotherapy (Wedleigh *et al* 1992).

For many years, uric acid has been used in clinical practice as a marker of several metabolic disturbances, although, until recently, its oxidants properties had not been considered (Angel *et al*, 2002). It has been specifically postulated that uric acid, the naturally occurring product of urine metabolism, may provide

endogenous natural protection against the oxidative injury occurring as a result of peroxynitrate exposure by acting as an endogenous free radical scavenger or oxidant (Warning 2002).

Leprosy imposes oxidative stress on its victims, which is further compounded by chemotherapy. In the more developed nations of America and Europe, the contributions of chemotherapy and antioxidants such as vitamin C, vitamin E and uric acid in the treatment of leprosy may have been well documented and dietary modification is fast becoming an acceptable part of the management protocol for this disorder. However, information on the oxidative status of Nigerian leprosy patients is scarce; in particular, very little attempts appear to have been made in this part of the world. Therefore the import of this study is to evaluate the effects of leprosy on non-enzymatic antioxidants (vitamin C, E and uric acid) in Edo state Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of eighty-six subjects comprising of seventy-one leprosy patients from Ossroino leprosarium specialist hospital, organ in Edo state. And another fifteen subjects who are apparently healthy, within the same age and sex and in similar socio-economic and environmental status served as control. Of the seventy-one lepers, thirty-one of them were on multidrug therapy (MDT) while forty were lepers relieved from therapy (RFT). The MDT group were further subdivided into (a) Ten paucibacillary (PB) leprosy patients and (b) twenty-one multibacillary (MB) leprosy patients. Informed consent was obtained from all subjects prior to the commencement of the experiment and sample collection. The subsequent biochemical analysis was carried out within two hours of sample collection.

Biochemical Assays:

All parameters namely, vitamin C, vitamin E and Uric acid were determined using standard procedures (Wadleigh; *et al* 1992, Sauberlich, *et al* 1994 and Roe and Kuelher, 1943). All kits used were commercially available test kits, products of Randox Laboratories, U.K. In all analyses, manufacturers instructions were adhered to strictly.

Statistical Analysis:

The group mean \pm SEM was calculated for each analyte and significant differences between means evaluated using the student t-test, with $P < 0.05$ considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this study, the non-enzymatic antioxidants (vitamin C, vitamin E and Uric acid) status of eighty-six subjects was investigated. The results obtained from this study showed a general decrease in the levels of vitamins C and E in lepers and an increase in uric acid in lepers

Table-1: The mean \pm SEM of vitamin C, E and Uric Acid in control and all leprosy subjects irrespective of drug status.

Group	N	Vitamin C g/dl	Vitamin E mg/dl	Uric acid mg/dl
Control	15	1.42 \pm 0.14	12.28 \pm 0.62	6.96 \pm 0.32
Leprosy Patients	71	0.53 \pm 0.03	6.22 \pm 0.29	7.30 \pm 0.74
P-value	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.05$

Table 2: Comparison between paucibacillary (PB) and multibacillary (MB) leprosy patients and controls

Group	N	Vitamin C g/dl	Vitamin E mg/dl	Uric acid mg/dl
Control	15	1.42 \pm 0.14	12.28 \pm 0.62	6.96 \pm 0.32
PB	10	0.51 \pm 0.07	6.64 \pm 0.53	2.50 \pm 0.26
MB	21	0.43 \pm 0.03	5.68 \pm 0.36	3.08 \pm 0.41
P-value		$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.05$

The antioxidants – vitamin C, E and Uric acid were significantly reduced ($P < 0.05$) in both paucibacillary
Table 3: Comparison of mean \pm SEM of antioxidants in PB and MB patient

Group	N	Vitamin C g/dl	Vitamin E mg/dl	Uric acid mg/dl
Patients on MDT	31	0.46 \pm 0.34	5.99 \pm 0.03	2.90 \pm 0.29
Patients RFT	40	0.58 \pm 0.05	6.40 \pm 0.46	10.72 \pm 0.99
P-value		$P > 0.05$	$P > 0.05$	$P < 0.05$

and multibacillary lepers when compared with the control subjects. The obvious negative influence of leprosy disease on the plasma levels of the antioxidants (vitamins C, E and Uric acid) studied as shown in tables 1 and 2 above agrees with the work of (Vigayaraghavan, *et al*; 2005); who reasoned that antioxidants may provide first line defense against reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated in disease conditions.

Table 4: Comparison of vitamins C, E and Uric acid of control with leprosy on MDT and RFT.

Group	N	Vitamin C g/dl	Vitamin E mg/dl	Uric acid mg/dl
PB Patients	10	0.51 \pm 0.07	6.64 \pm 0.53	2.50 \pm 0.26
MB Patients	21	0.43 \pm 0.03	5.68 \pm 0.36	3.08 \pm 0.41
P-value		$P > 0.05$	$P > 0.05$	$P > 0.05$

Table 5: Comparison of vitamin C, E and Uric acid in all patients on MDT and those on RFT

Group	N	Vitamin C g/dl	Vitamin E mg/dl	Uric acid mg/dl
Control	15	1.42 \pm 0.14	12.28 \pm 0.62	6.96 \pm 0.32
Patients on MDT	31	0.46 \pm 0.03	5.99 \pm 0.03	2.90 \pm 0.29
Patients RFT	40	0.58 \pm 0.05	6.40 \pm 0.45	10.72 \pm 0.99
P-value		$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.05$	$P < 0.05$

Leprosy continues to afflict a large number of people globally as shown from several studies (Gandhi and Singh, 2004). The antioxidants (Vitamins C, E and Uric acid) status of these patients investigated in this study revealed a statistically significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) when compared with the control subjects. This suggests that leprosy patients, irrespective of their drug therapy status or disease type, have significantly reduced levels of antioxidants. In an earlier study, Florence (1995) concluded that all leprosy patients had a mild to moderate lowering of antioxidants especially when nutrition and immunological status of the patients are compromised. This reduction being with not only the disease, per se, but also with poverty, as all leprosy patients belonged to the low economic status.

Though the antioxidants were generally low, a closer look at the two disease types revealed that antioxidants vitamin C and Vitamin E were higher in PB leprosy than those of MB ($p < 0.05$). Hooper (2000) had shown that PB leprosy patients have higher immunity compared with the MB group. This could be as a result of their low bacterial load of the causative organism *M. Leprae*. Also PB patients are endowed with the ability to eliminate bacteria through cell – mediated immunity, next to resistant normal controls (Hooper *et al*; 2000, Lopez, 1994 and Kelly *et al*; 1990).

From table four, vitamin C and E in both patients on MDT and those RFT were markedly reduced ($P < 0.05$) compared with the controls. This indicates that current or previous exposure to MDT generally had an effect on the antioxidant status of leprosy patients. There is overwhelming evidence to prove that dapsone, one of the MDT drugs for leprosy is strongly oxidative and induces hemolysis. This increases free radicals and subsequently reduces the oxidants. Kelly *et al*; 1990, Lardo *et al*, 1997). In this work, the level of uric acid (table 4) was lower in patients on MDT compared with those RFT and normal controls (Lardo *et al*, 1997). Kong and Lillehi (1998) suggested from their work that over production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) following therapy exhausts the production of adaptive oxidants defenses.

Of particular enthusiasm in this study however, is the value of Uric acid obtained for the two leprosy groups (MDT and RFT). Leprosy patients on MDT had significantly decreased level of uric acid ($p < 0.05$) compared with controls and those RFT. On the other hand, leprosy patients RFT showed significantly increased level ($p < 0.05$) compared with control and MDT patients (tables 4 and 5). The observed decrease in the uric acid level in all leprosy patients on MDT could be due to the presence of ROS resulting from the therapeutic drugs, which the uric acid tries to mop-up, i.e. a decrease in antioxidant potential

Uric acid is a strong peroxynitrite (ONOO^-) scavenger demonstrated by the capacity to bind peroxynitrite but not nitric oxide (NO). Patients with multiple sclerosis have been shown to have significantly lower levels of Uric acid than controls (Angel, *et al*; 2002) probably this is what is happening in this of leprosy.

This study amongst other things suggests that Nigerian leprosy patients irrespective of whether they are on multi drug therapy (MDT) or relieved from therapy (RFT) have lowered plasma non-enzymatic antioxidants (vitamin C, E and Uric acid) except for those RFT whose Uric acid has a high level than those on MDT and control subjects. The free radical producing ability from drugs used in the MDT and the influence of *M. leprae* seemed to have a reducing effect on the antioxidants capacity of the patients. Antioxidants are best supplied by balanced diet, but unfortunately leprosy patients are of the low socio-economic status. Therefore, it is reasonable to say that there is need for intervention with antioxidants supplements.

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